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ORIGINAL ARTICLE

TEACHERS' CAPACITY DEVELOPMENT AND TEACHER'S EFFECTIVENESS IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN BAYELSA STATE

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Abstract

The study investigated the teachers' capacity development and effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State. The researcher adopted the correlational research design for the study. The Krejcie and Morgan formula for sample determination was used to determine the sample size. The formula gave the sample size to be 335 teachers from a population of 2776 teachers in secondary schools in three local government areas in Bayelsa State. The instruments used for data collection in this study were two sets of instruments: The teachers Capacity Development Questionnaire (TCDQ) and the Teachers Job Effectiveness Questionnaire (TJEQ). The first instrument is a self-constructed instrument titled "Teacher's Capacity Development Questionnaire (TCDQ)," it was divided into two sections (A and B). Section A consisted of items on personal data such as age, gender, marital status etc., section B contained statement items that will focus on teacher capacity development. B The second instrument "Teachers Job Effectiveness Questionnaire (TJEQ)," was also self-constructed and that consist of 34 associated items. Both TCDQ and TJEQ were structured on a 4-point Likert scale of strongly Agree (SA)=4, Agree (A)=3, Disagree (D)=2 and Strongly Disagree (SD)=1. Respondents are expected to choose one option for each statement item. The findings of the study revealed that in-service training, which is relevant courses and activities on which a teacher may participate to upgrade his/her professional knowledge, skills and competence in the teaching profession has a significant positive relationship with teachers effectiveness. Based on the findings, the researcher recommended Government and school heads should pay more attention to in-service training, as the study reveals that it can enhance teachers' effectiveness the most. Teaching should undergo in-service training at least once a term. Government should make it mandatory for all teachers in public secondary schools to t ICT compliant. Since most government schools lack ICT gadgets, the government should bear the cost of providing ICT gadgets and also ensure that teachers are regularly trained on the use of ICT gadgets.

Keywords: Teachers', Public, Secondary, Schools, Bayelsa State.

INTRODUCTION

The effectiveness of a teacher is reflected in the discharge of his/her duty. In an educational institution just like any other organization, effectiveness is a critical factor. It is common to measure organizations use to access performance. It is the main focus of any school system to achieve its mission, goals, objectives, and vision. The effectiveness determines the political objectives of the organization or the degree to which an organization realizes its own goals. According to Ukeje, Okorie and Nwagbara as cited in Amanchukwu (2018) they asserted that the ultimate goal of formal organization is effectiveness, that the effectiveness of educational institution to the extent, to which the student and the teachers are satisfied. The staff morale is high and the student's dropout rate is low.

Effectiveness is simply doing the right thing. Ololube (2009) summed up effectiveness as: Doing the right thing; obtaining aims and objectives; optimal utilization of resources; obtaining positive results; creative and imaginative; factors that influences. In a nutshell, the attainment of goals and objectives is the optimal responsibility of a teacher in the school system. It is therefore apparent that the operation of the educational system depends largely on the effectiveness of the teacher.

Teachers play a major role in ensuring that students in secondary school attain quality education as much as possible. Today, teachers need to be competent to meet the requirements of changing classroom practices. As an agent of change, teachers can promote quality education and improve students' performance. Teachers should remain the essential actors and catalysts for change in all efforts aimed at promoting quality education in schools. Teachers' effectiveness is consistently related to teachers' behaviour and student outcome. A teacher who is the vehicle of force in the educational system ought to be constantly updated to meet the demands of the current changes in Pedagogy content, skills and learning technology.

According to Okeke (2004), a teacher embraces all who discover, or order, transmit, disseminate, appraise or administer in any learning and teaching process. In the same vein, Asiabaka and Emenalo (2011) define a teacher as a human catalyst who intentionally influences an interaction by structuring and restructuring the environment of the learner in such a way that the latter will acquire desired knowledge, skills, attitude and meaningful contribution to the development of humanity at an appropriate time.

From authors/scholars definitions and descriptions of a teacher, it can be deduced, that the teacher has the key to knowledge, skill and attitudes of the willing learners. Hence, FRN (2014) posits that no education system can rise above the quality of its teachers. Students' academic performance in both internal and external exams had been used to determine the effectiveness of a teacher, perhaps, the teacher failure to achieve goals might be attributed to the poor nature of capacity development programmes.

Capacity development is an essential ingredient in the process of

changing individuals and organizations from where they are and to where they should be and operate. United Nation Development Programme (UNDP) (2009) sees capacity development as a process through which individuals, organizations and societies obtain strengthens and maintain the capabilities to set and achieve their development objectives over time. Capacity development is believed to better express an approach that builds on existing skills and knowledge driving a dynamic and flexible process of change.

Every organization that is goal-oriented needs to be concerned about the capacity development of staff. Capacity development encompasses human resources development. It is based on the concept that education and training be at the heart of development efforts and without HRD most development interventions will be ineffective. HRD focuses on a service of actions directed at helping the participant in the development process to increase their knowledge, skills and understanding and to develop the attitude needed to bring about desired development and change (Abdul, 2002). Human beings become productive resources only when they are able and in a position to contribute meaningfully.

However, in a bid to improve the learning outcome of secondary schools students, the Bayelsa State, restoration government declare a state of emergency on education 2012 on the assumption of office. The state government also intended to meet the 8-millennium development goals (MDGs) by the United Nations pledge of which universal basic education is inclusive. The government of Bayelsa State in conjunction with NC (local content conducted a six week) teacher capacity development training in 2018 and 2019-to address the inadequacies in the sector. But despite government commitment in (financial, manpower, school, facilities, infrastructures ICT facilities and teaching of training) there seems to be and remarkable improvement, because it is poorly co-ordinated, it does not cut across the board and majority of teachers are yet to benefit significantly.

However, for this study among the various capacity development programmers identified, the researcher is interested in investigating the provision of capacity development programmers in secondary school Bayelsa State in respect to workshop/seminars, conference, ICT training coaching/mentoring draining /retraining and welfare and empowerment. Therefore effectively designed and organize capacity development programmes such as listed above, have the tendency to result in teacher professional development whereby teachers are exposed to new knowledge, techniques tests are likely to add value to the teaching and non-teaching responsibilities capacity development programmers ought to enrich teacher and also contribute t the attainment of the goals of secondary education. It is against this background that the stud intends to find out the level of capacity development programmers provision for teachers in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The observation in recent years is that the academic performance of

students is declining in both internal and external examinations especially in West Africa Senior Secondary Examination (WASSE), National Examination Council (NECO) and Joint Admission and Matriculation Board (JAMB) despite the government huge budget allocation on education. The declining academic performance of students in the public secondary is of great concern among education stakeholders. The fear is whether this performance of students depends on the teacher effectiveness.

Consequently, the main thrust of this study is to investigate the extent to which capacity development programs such as in-service training, mentoring, teachers professional development programmes, ICT training and induction and orientation programmes influence the effectiveness of teachers in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

This chapter deals with the review of related literature organized in the following heading: Theoretical Framework; Conceptual Framework; Empirical Study and Summary of Literature Review.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study is anchored on the human capital development theory propounded by Gary Becker in 1964 as cited in Kio (2019). The theory emphasized that the training and retraining of the workforce will increase the effectiveness of the worker and consequently result in an increase in productivity.

The human capital theory stresses the significance of education and training as the key to participation in the new global economy. The success of any nation in terms of human development is largely dependent upon the physical and human capital stock. Thus, recent social research focuses on the behavioural sciences of humanity about economic productivity. Generally, human capital represents the assets each individual develops to enhance economic productivity. The theory emphasized how education increases the productivity and efficiency of workers by increasing the level of cognitive stock of economically productive human capability, which is a product of innate abilities and investment in human beings. The provision of formal education is seen as a productive investment in human capital, which the proponents of the theory have considered as equally or even more equally worthwhile than that of physical capital. In schools, the human capital development programmes that are provided for teachers are aimed at improving their professional competency. Teachers in the school system need development programmes to meet up with the global changes. This is true because society in this 21st century is moving towards changes in technology. Therefore, teachers should be trained and retrained to be able to catch up with the changes in society. Teachers in school need to be trained to meet the relevant needs of the students. In other words teacher's needs development programmes to achieve set objectives of education and to be able to carry out other duties.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK CAPACITY DEVELOPMENT

Capacity development is a term that is commonly used by any development-oriented organization. UNDP (2009) defines capacity development as a process through which individuals, organizations and Societies obtain, strengthen and maintain the capabilities to set and achieve their development objectives over time. It is the engine of human development.

Other definitions of capacity development include as cited in Davies (2018) the process of enhancing, improving and unleashing capacity, it is a form of change that focuses on improvement (European centre for Development Policy Management ECDPM). United States Agency for International Development (USAID) affirms that it is approaches strategies or methodologies used by USAID and its stakeholders to charge transform and improve u performance at the individual, organizational sector or broad system level. World Bank Institute (WBI) posit that it is a locally driven process of learning by leaders, coalition and other agents of change that brings about changes on socio-political policy-related and organizational factors to enhance local ownership for and effectiveness and efficiency of efforts to achieve development goal. Civil Defence Emergency Management Group (CDEM) insist that capacity development encompasses the traditional scope of professional development (skills-based training, knowledge-based education and experience) but also incorporates other aspects including relationship, mandate and direction, cool and work environment, time and motivation and the previously acquired knowledge and skills the person in their role.

Capacity Development is a process of enabling or empowering individuals, organizations to continuously attain their goals and achieve their objects and retain their relevance through the instrumentality of their human resources.

In fact, in countries such as Singapore, every teacher is required to submit him/herself to 300 hours of retraining every year. Therefore, capacity development is an inevitable tool for effectiveness. Ibukun (2004) expressed that teachers should go for training programmes through appropriate seminars, workshop symposia, conferences etc. Therefore, for capacity development to be effective, it must respond to the growth and development needs of the individuals as well those of the relevant institution.

Need for Capacity Development

- *To ensure survival, relevance and consequent development of the organization.*
- *For organizations to be able to withstand the negative impacts of globalisation, competition, liberalizations, blurred political bondage vis-a-vis economic and social forces.*
- *Modem day development of societies and organizations is determined by the quantity and quality of knowledge they possess and can indecently deploy.*
- *Rapid changes e. ICT, technological break thought, democratization etc.*

- *Dead of results of landlessness and ignorance.*
- *Identification of optimal deployment of resources.*
- *Increased teacher/human effectiveness and productivity.*
- *To develop the capacity to anticipate and adapt to emerging challenges (Asodike & Ebong, 2012).*

Capacity development programmes include

The under-listed are some of the capacity development programmes that a teacher can undertake.

- *Seminar/workshops/conferences*
- *Guided familiarity with relevant infract reties*
- *Study tools*
- *ICT training*
- *In-service training*
- *Professional growth and development*
- *Apprenticeship,*
- *Coaching/mentoring*
- *Research*
- *Welfare/empowerment*

This work, however, will be limited to seminar/workshop/conferences, ICT Training, self-development in-service training and Empowerment.

Capacity Development on Education

Education is a process of discipline through training and study in the acquisition of skills and knowledge, a process of acculturation by which the individuals is helped to attain the development of his potentialities and their maximum activation when necessary according to right reasons and to achieve thereby, his perfect self-fulfilment (Okaor as cited in Anuforo, 2008).

Education is universally acknowledged as an essential tool in the process of national development to empower people with knowledge, skills, values and attitude to improve their quality of life, enhance productivity and capacity to learn new skills that may enable them to participate more fully in the development process. Therefore education is essential to human development because it is considered a human right. Ajeyalemi (2006) pointed that education is a human right that should be given to all human beings. Education from junior to senior secondary school level is supposed to be the bedrock and foundation towards higher knowledge in tertiary institutions. It is an investment as well as an instrument that can be used to achieve a more rapid economic social, political, technological specific and cultural development in the country. FRN (2014) stipulated that secondary education is an instrument for the national development that fosters the worth and development of the individual for further education and general development of the society and equality of educational

opportunity to all Nigerian children, irrespective of any real or marginal disabilities.

The government of Nigeria intended to meet the eight (8) Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) by 2015 by the United Nations pledge of which universal basic education is inclusive. To achieve the mission, there is a need for qualified and competent teachers which in turn is expected into the excellent performance of teaching and learning which cannot be overemphasized.

Teacher Capacity Development

A teacher in a specific term is one whose occupation is to teach. According to Anyaogu and Anugon as cited in Monica (2016) a teacher engages in interactive behaviour with one or more students to effect a change in the behaviour of students. The teacher is used as a synonym for educator tutor, instructor, master, mistress, governess, educationist, preceptor, achiever etc. Okeke (2004) opines that the teacher embraces all who discover, or order, transmit disseminate, appraise, or administer in any learning and teaching process. Ezeani (2006) sees a teacher as one who engages in interactive behaviour with one or more students to effect a change in those students behaviour. In the same vein, Asiabaka and Emenalo (2011) defined a teacher as a human catalyst who intentionally influences an interaction by structuring and restructuring the environment of the learner in such a way that the latter will acquire desired knowledge, skills and attitudes and meaningful contribution to the development c humanity at an appropriate time. A teacher is a person who had undergone approved professional training in education at appropriate levels capable of imparting knowledge and skill to the learner (FRN, 2014). From the authors/scholars, definitions and descriptions of a teacher can be deduced that the teacher is a critical factor in any educational institution; a teacher has the key to knowledge, skill and attitude.

Teacher development has to do with equipping the teacher with all necessary skills needed for their improved satisfactory job performance. According to Emechebe (2009), since a well-developed teacher is likely to perform better than his counterpart without formal training, the need arises to design training and development programmes to ensure their high productivity work. This teacher capacity development tends to improve the performance of teachers and the standard of education. Emechebe (2009) noted that teacher development is effective in teacher professional growth and the attainment of organizational goals. It, therefore, ensures the following:

- *Teachers to be more productive*
- *The teacher has more confidence in his ability to work; he/she enjoys his work and high morale.*
- *Teacher to new methods and skills relevant to their job*
- *It also exposes them to correct issues in question*
- *Teacher to adaptability to change*

The above statements reveal that teacher capacity development is linked

with effective work for professional growth. Azuzor as cited in Kio (2019) added that for teachers to perform effectively well on their jobs, there must be the provision of a policy of sending them on training to acquire relevant skills. However, it is when teachers are adequately trained and developed those educational institutions can be assured of a supply of qualified participants who will contribute to educational growth.

The Need for Teacher Capacity Development

According to Ukeje in Madumere-Obike (2008), the challenge to teacher development programmes in Nigeria rests on the production of an insufficient number of knowledgeable skilful competent and committed properly oriented and positively motivated teachers in a period of: extreme educational expansion. This is not an easy task for sustainable educational development many school teachers still emphasize the old traditional way of teaching thereby encouraging their students to be content with the notes given to them by their teachers. Unfortunately, society, the student/pupils and the subject matter that needs to be taught changes work, especially with technological advancement. It is important to state that the rate at which fewer changes emerge does not help an inadequately prepared teacher to cope with Ejiogu as cited in Madumere-Obike (2005) thinks that the goal of development would be to secure the professional growth of the teachers, to improve the performance of both teachers and school, and increase the satisfaction of individuals and co-operate needs with the system. It is therefore paramount that the teachers need to change with time, to answer the call for sustainable and qualitative education. Onwumere (2006) asserted that education is the pivot on which nation development revolves it is the springboard for socio-political, economic and cultural development. There is a need for teachers to be continuously trained for them to be able to pursue and achieve the national objectives. FRN (2014) made provision for the development of teachers when it stated that teacher education will continue to take cognizance of the changes in methodology and the curriculum. The teacher will be regularly exposed to innovation. Their professional in-service training developed as an integral part of continuing teacher education.

Teacher capacity developments have become an accepted phenomenon in educational institutions. The development programmes are considered very critical. They are planned activities that focus on increasing and enlarging the capabilities improving the technical and conceptual skills of teachers so that they can possess the necessary abilities to handle complex situations and better perform their job.

In-Service training

The need for training and retraining of teachers cannot be underestimated; it is a necessity in enhancing effectiveness. The absence of in-service training of teachers will retard the professional growth of teachers as well as widen gaps between demands and school achievements level. In-service

training education can simply be defined as the relevant courses and activities on which an I teacher may participate to upgrade his/her professional knowledge, skills and competence in the teaching profession therefore, it encompasses all forms of education and training given to a [teacher who is already on the job of teaching and learning.

Organization (educational system) are facing many changes which are related to economic, In social and technological needs, such as to meet the growing global needs, training programme plays an important part to overcome these problems and to cater the needs of the organization. The need for training teachers is very important to improve the quality of education in Nigeria. Teachers are crucial in implementing educational reforms by the aspirations of the national policy of education. FRN (2014) asserted that no level of education can raise above I the quality of the teacher. The higher the level of educational attainment by the teacher the higher the level of education standard in the country.

The Need for In-Service Training for Teachers

The need for in-service training in school has become an accepted phenomenon in educational institutions. They are planned activities that focus on increasing and enlarging the capabilities, improving the technical and conceptual skills of staff so that they can possess the necessary abilities to handle complex situations and face innovations and reformations. In service, training can enhance the professionalism of teachers who can in turn contribute to the organizational goal achievement.

In service, training is a fundamental aspect for the enhancement of teachers professionalism related to the teacher's vision to improve the quality of their work. It provides teachers with ample opportunities to learn new concepts, methods and approaches through professional development.

In service, training increases organisational productivity. They enable the teacher to effectively manipulate materials resources to achieve organizational self objectives. It furnishes teachers with current ideas and methodologies to make the school system more attractive. Olanyinjan and Ojo (2008) submitted that physical, social intellectual and mental training is highly essential in the facilitation of the productively and development of organizational personnel's that recognise the need for a teacher in an institution to grow.

The Importance of Training

According to Kio (2019) the importance of training includes;

1. *Expenses on training are an investment and not a wastage*
2. *It relates to a special job*
3. *It is beneficial for organization and employee*
4. *Training is a continuous process*
5. *It is essential for both new and old employees*
6. *Training is necessary for all managerial levels*
7. *It helps to prepare employees for higher jobs by developing advanced*

skills in them.

8. *It improves the overall performance of the organization*
9. *It reduces the number of accidents*
10. *To provide the proper training schedule for employees and motivate people in the organization*

Benefits of Training to the Teacher

According to Nwabueze (2011), the benefits of training teachers include:

1. ***Faster in learning new skills:*** *Training help employee to reduce the learning time of their subject area and achieve higher standards of academic performance.*
2. ***Increased productivity:*** *Training increases the skills of the new employee while performing a particular job. An increased skill level usually helps in increasing both the quantity and quality of output.*
3. ***Lesser need for supervision:*** *A trained employee needs lesser supervision. Training does not eliminate the need for supervision but it reduces the need for detailed and **constant** supervision*
4. ***Increasing confidence:*** *Training creates a feeling of confidence in the minds of employees, who feel comfortable while handling newer challenges, it gives a feeling of safety and security to them at the workplace.*
5. ***Career advancement:*** *Training among teachers leads to career development. It helps them to grow to fester in knowledge and skills.*
6. ***Increases safety:*** *trained teachers especially those teaching science subjects handle the laboratory equipment safely. They also know the use of various safety devices in the laboratories to facilitate teaching, thus they are less prone to accidents.*

Government Policy on In-Service Training of Teachers

The National policy on education (NPE) in Nigeria had undergone many reviews since its inception in 1977. The prominent role of teacher education has been adequately highlighted in the National I policy of Education (FGN, 2014). The policy stressed in section 70 (0) that since no education system may rise above the quality of a teacher, teacher education shall continue to be given major emphasis in all educational planning and development. Owolabi (2005) pointed out that I policies of teacher education deal with what the relevant authorities are meant to be carried out continually to enhance the quality of teacher education.

The FRN (2014) emphasized the significance of in-service training of teachers so that education can be advantageously employed to fulfil national philosophy, thus, the policy states that;

- i) *Teachers' education will continue to take cognizance of changes in methodology and the curriculum.*
- ii) *Teachers will be regularly exposed to innovation in their profession.*

iii) In-service training will be developed as an integral part of continuing education, no matter the efficiency of the pre-service training, we give to researchers there will always be areas of inadequacy the policy which the government put in place made it deal that teachers training and retraining is highly recognized.

Teachers' Information Communication and Technology (ICT) Training

Research has shown that the knowledge acquired through information, communication and technology (ICT) training for teachers, enhances effective teaching and learning in schools. Borg (2018) reported a significant relationship between teacher's knowledge of information, communication and technology (ICT) literacy and their job performance, the findings show that the more knowledgeable a teacher is in the use of ICT, the more productive the teacher will be in his/her teaching job.

Integration of ICT in Teacher Professional Development

The integration of ICT in teacher professional development according to Anderson and Allen in Hooker (2009) involves two sets of activities or roles. One is training teachers to know about ICT and its use in teaching as a computer is introduced to schools. The other role of ICT is as a means of providing teacher education either as a core or main component of a programme or playing a supplementary role within it as shown in fig 1 below.

Core Technology

<p>ICT use in the Classroom as a content focus to use of the teacher learning how to use ICT</p>	<p>ICT is used as the core technology for participation Learning via ICT</p>
<p>ICT use in the classroom as part of method curriculum and lesson planning.</p>	<p>ICT is used to facilitate some (non-essential aspects of participation complementary technology.</p>

Table 2.1

Two dimensions of ICT integration in teacher professional development
Source: Adopted from Hooker (2009).

Some key principles of good practice emerge from the use of ICT, but primarily for their use of any teacher capacity development scheme.

- a) The need to shift from education for ICT to the use of ICT for education is a fundamental shift in focus from training teachers for ICT technical skills to supporting teachers in the use of ICT for educational enhancement.*
- b) The need to focus on sustainable, resource, adequate and ongoing professional development to ensure the effective deployments of ICT.*
- c) Teachers and teacher education should genuinely (own) the process of ICT integration to enable them to be creative in adapting ICT to their classroom circumstances.*

- d) *The need to contribute pre-service and in-service initiatives balancing support to both environments.*
- e) *The need for ICT to be integrated across curricular in a blended way*
- f) *The need for locally produced content that is relevant to teachers and learners. (Imfundo, Union & Olakulehin, as cited in Hooker, 2009).*

Teacher Professional Development Programme

Teacher professional development is about teachers learning, learning how to learn, and transforming their knowledge into practice for the benefit of their students' growth (Bautista & Ortega-Ruiz, 2015). Teacher Professional development involves many processes, actions, and mechanisms that are inevitably mediated by the cultural, social, political, and economic features and conditions of each particular context (Tan & Dimmock, 2014). Professional development is frequently reserved for continuous professional development in schools; professional development is viewed as the body of systematic activities to prepare teachers for their job, including initial training, induction courses, in-service training, and continuous professional development within school settings. According to McCaughtry, Cothran, Kulinna, Martin and Faust (2006) the objectives of teachers' development programmes includes;

- *To update individuals' knowledge of a subject in light of recent advances in the area;*
- *To update individuals' skills, attitudes and approaches in light of the development of new teaching techniques and objectives, new circumstances and new educational research;*
- *To enable individuals to apply changes made to curricula or other aspects of teaching practice;*
- *To enable schools to develop and apply new strategies concerning the curriculum and other aspects of teaching practice;*
- *To exchange information and expertise among teachers and others, e.g. academics, f industrialists; and*
- *To help weaker teachers become more effective.*

Teacher professional development programmes can be provided in many ways, ranging from the formal to the informal. It can be made available through external expertise in the form of courses, workshops or formal qualification programmes, through collaboration between schools or teachers across schools (e.g. observational visits to other schools or teacher networks) or within the schools in which teachers work. In this last case, development can be provided through the educational seminar, workshop, conference, and the sharing of good practices.

Acheru (2008) highlighted the available training programmes for teachers on the job as follows;

- 1) **Seminar:** *In this case, teachers attend seminars and it is conducted twice a year, one for science teachers and the other for art teachers. Qualified*

instructors are invited as guest speakers to train teachers on how to cope with the challenges that emerge in the teaching/learning process.

- 2) **Workshops and conferences:** *Teachers also attend workshops and conferences to improve on the job. The method used in seminars, workshops and conferences includes lecturing, discussion, demonstration etc.*

Teacher Induction/Orientation

Induction is a term commonly used by organizations to mean a programme of events where recruits are introduced to their colleagues and working environment. Nel, Van Dyk, Haasbroek, Sono and Wemer (2006) assert that the last step in the staffing process is induction, which is also known as employee socialization. Induction is defined as exposure to something unknown; an act or process of inducting; an initial experience (Mish, as cited in Robinson, 1998). Induction for new teachers is the term used to describe a process or series of processes a beginning teacher experiences to improve the skills necessary in being successful in the assigned teaching environment (Gill, 2010). Orientation is the direction or introduction to an unfamiliar situation, an activity of a new kind; a program set up for the benefit of new employees. It is common in most schools.

The objectives of orientation and induction include: to help new employees settle into their environment; to help them understand their responsibilities; and ensure that the organization receives the benefits of a well-trained and highly motivated employee as quickly as possible (Robinson, 1998).

Grobler, Wamich, Carrelli, Elbert, and Hartfield (2002) stated some objectives of an effective induction programme, they are:

- *To make new employees more rapidly productive;*
- *To reduce fear and insecurity, reduction of labour turnover;*
- *Helping to create realistic employee expectations;*
- *Create job satisfaction and a positive attitude towards the employer;*
- *Saving the time of supervisors and colleagues; and*
- *A better understanding of the organization vision, mission and strategic aims.*

Lunenburg (2011) gave some guidelines as it concerns induction and orientation. They include:

- *Principals need to schedule beginning teacher orientation in addition to regular teacher orientation. Beginning teachers need to attend both sessions.*
- *Principals need to appoint someone to help beginning teachers set up their classrooms.*
- *Principals need to provide beginning teachers with a proper mix of courses, students, facilities (not all leftovers). If possible, lighten their load for the first year.*
- *Principals need to provide for joint planning, team teaching, committee*

assignments, and other cooperative arrangements between new and experienced teachers.

- *Principals need to issue newsletters that report on the accomplishments of all teachers, especially beginning teachers.*
- *Principals need to schedule reinforcing events, involving beginning and experienced teachers, such as tutor-tutor luncheons, parties, and awards.*
- *Principals need to provide regular (monthly) meetings between the beginning teacher and supervisor (mentor) to identify problems as soon as possible and to make recommendations for improvement.*
- *Principals need to carry on the regular evaluation of beginning teachers; evaluate strengths and weaknesses, present new information, demonstrate new skills and provide opportunities for practice and feedback.*

The development of an induction programme has increased, especially in the last two decades.

Induction programmes are very diverse and generally, they are linked to the unique culture of the country and to the local needs of the specific educational contexts within which they function.

Teachers' Mentoring

Mentoring comes from the root word 'mentor' which is a noun, mentoring it as a verb describes the process. Mentoring is a system where people with a lot of experience, knowledge, etc advise and help other people at work or young people preparing for work (Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English, as cited in Abali, 2017). In the school system, Koki (1997) defines mentoring in education as a complex and multi-dimensional process of guiding, teaching, influencing and supporting a beginning or new teacher. It requires that a senior teacher or person should be made responsible to bring about behavioural change in a new teacher and ensuring his professional development to be more effective in the teaching and learning process.

1. *It is a relationship -between mentor and mentee, and a reciprocal one.*
2. *It is intentional. Both determined and decided to enter into the relationship.*
3. *It is formal -at work or in a work situation.*
4. *It is a nurturing process that fosters the development of the mentee towards his full potential.*
5. *It is collaborative and beneficial/rewarding to both parties.*
6. *It is based on or characterized by mutual trust and belief.*

As it concerns teachers, the concept of mentoring requires that a senior teacher or person should be made responsible to bring about behavioural change in the newcomer and ensure his professional development to be more effective in the teaching and learning process.

Gill (2010) identified two categories of mentors for teachers. The first will be an experienced instructor, hopefully within the same building as the new hire and another trade and industrial instructor, even if the mentor teaches in an instructional area different from the new hire. This mentor's educational responsibility will be to work with the new hire addressing issues with! lesson plan writing, student assessment and grades, classroom and/or laboratory management issues, and general school district policy. This role is similar in many ways to the role of supervising a teacher working with a student-teacher. The second type of mentor for the new will be an experienced teacher teaching in the same trade/instructional area as the new teacher. In the same vein, Kram, as cited in Javed and Iqbal (2015) classified the functions of a mentor into two types: profession related function and psychosocial functions. He further elaborated that the profession related functions included providing training to the mentee, teaching required skills enabling the mentee to assume responsibilities, providing information, assigning challenging tasks, introducing self-evaluation, providing inspiration, guidance and advice, whereas psychosocial functions included role modelling, counselling and instructions, acceptance and access as well as intimate relations with a mentee.

Furthermore, Britnor-Guest (2001) identified several organizational benefits including improved performance and efficiency, interpersonal communication skills, high spirit and boosted morale, devotion and dedication, effective recruitment and retention of staff, other educational benefits of mentoring according to Alabi (2017) include: Providing on-the-job training opportunity for teachers; Ensuring teachers' retention on the job; Supporting teachers' maximum performance (output) in teaching; Encouraging teachers' aspiration for excellence in the profession; Developing teachers' competence in handling administrative matters; Developing teachers' interest in teaching improving teachers' relationship skills; Impacting and being impacted by others in the teaching profession.

Abali (2017) noted areas that new teachers can be mentored. They include:

- 1) School records keeping: *Identifying the school records to be kept, understanding the need and importance of school records to be kept, recording into and or marking of the school records and f keeping and proper maintenance of the school records being kept etc.*
- 2) Classroom management (skills/control): *Proper arrangement of the learners and their seats, keeping classroom neat, orderliness -the arrangement of wall pictures, charts and posters, making use of eye contact in classroom control, proper selection and involvement of class captain or monitor and instilling self-discipline in the learners etc.*
- 3) Teaching effectiveness and efficiency: *Understanding different teaching methods and using the best method (eclectic) of teaching each topic, use of effective teaching apparatus, proper evaluation of learning outcomes, adequate preparation for teaching etc.*
- 4) School community relations: *Being friendly with all in the school, being*

cooperative with all the colleagues, developing skills of a good relationship with all colleagues and school authority as well, working or striving for the peace, progress and stability of the school community.

- 5) School -community relations: *Being friendly with all the people in the school community most especially parents of the students in the school, being approachable by all in the community, contributing to the peace, progress and stability of the community at large etc.*
- 6) School plant management: *Ensuring that the school environment is neat always by inculcating such into his students so they maintain neat classrooms and the school as a whole, ensuring that lawns are well kept, and ensuring proper maintenance of school facilities, f equipment and even building. Reporting any damages in the school plant to the appropriate I quarters or authorities for immediate repair etc.*
- 7) Evaluation and assessment of students: *Identifying different methods of evaluating and assessing students and applying the most appropriate ones at different situations, giving students outcomes of the assessment or evaluation and making use of the outcomes to make decisions and take actions.*

Effectiveness

Effectiveness in teaching could be viewed as a communication process of a human undertaking whose purpose is to help people bring about the expected change in behaviour so that they can become good productive citizens. Effectiveness is common to measure organizations use to access performance.

Zherg (2010) opined that effectiveness determines the policy objectives of the organization or the degree to which an organization realizes its own goals. Effectiveness is about doing the right thing while efficiency is doing right. Drucker as cited in Ololube (2009) opined that effectiveness is the foundation for success, efficiency is the minimum condition for survival, efficiency is concerned with doing things right, effectiveness is doing the right things.

Table2:2

The difference between efficiency and effectiveness in job performance

Efficiency	Effectiveness
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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Doing things right - Sage guard resources - Conform to duties, reduce cost - Follow rules and regulations - Minimal efforts in problem-solving - Judged by the number of outputs - The minimum condition for survival 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Does the right things. - Optimal utilization of resources. - Obtain positive results - Maximize project - Attain aims and objective - Creative and imaginative - Factors that influence success is carried out as the foundation for success
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Source: (Ololube, 2009).

Nwoye, and Umoh, (2018) made a distinctive differentiation between effectiveness and efficiency. Effectiveness is the accomplishment of the recognized objective of cooperative action and that the degree of accomplishment indicates the degree of effectiveness. He went further to explain that apparently, an objective of the co-operation is non-personal being, an aim of the system of co-operation as a whole efficiency of a co-operation system is the resultant of the 1 efficiency. Effectiveness is the capability of producing the desired result or the ability to produce K desired output. When something is deemed effective, it means it has an intended or expected outcome or produces a deep vivid impression.

Effectiveness versus Efficiency

Mouzas (2006) emphasized two indicators to assess performance, efficiency and effectiveness. The two might be synonymous yet each of these is different.

The findings revealed that efficient information provides different data compared to effectiveness.

Fig 2.1

Efficiency and Effectiveness Information process.

Source: adapted from Frey and Widmer (2009).

According to Heilman and Kennedy-Phillips (2011), organizational effectiveness helps to assess the progress towards mission fulfilment and goal achievement to improve organization effectiveness management should strive for better communication, interaction, leadership direction adaptability and a positive environment.

Lastly, Effectiveness oriented teachers must be concerned about output, it measures the achievement of goals and objectives of the school system, therefore, the effectiveness of a teacher in the school system is reflected in the discharge of his/her duty. In conclusion, the attainment of goals, objective mission and vision of the educational institution greatly depends on the teacher doing the thing.

Teacher Effectiveness

Effective teachers are those who achieve the goal which they set for themselves or which they set for them by others like the Ministry of Education (Lorin, 2004). An effective teacher is a teacher who produces desired results in the course of his duty (Uchefuna, 2001). Furthermore, changes in classroom and teaching curriculum etc. can cause a decrease or increase in teacher effectiveness (Lorin, 2004).

The following are properties of an effective teacher:

Professionalism: An effective teacher is committed to his job, is confident, respects all persons and is trustworthy.

Leadership: An effective teacher is accountable, flexible and has a passion for learning. **Reasoning:** An effective teacher thinks logically and recognizes cause and effects.

Expectation: An effective teacher is initiative, seeks information sets and meets challenging targets (Lorin, 2004).

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An effective teacher delivers his/her lessons on time, can attend to

students' problems and correct them when necessary record all results on time, update all school records, makes fewer notes and assignments.

According to Awoniyi as cited by Ogbu (2013) a teacher can join skills with the right behaviour to achieve the school objectives. Bonghtons (2009) opines that an effective the teacher keeps abreast in his/her field and can communicate knowledge effectively to others at a level that is commensurable with their knowledge.

REVIEW OF EMPIRICAL LITERATURE In-Service Training and Effectiveness

Fejoh and Faniran (2016) examined the Impact of in-service training and staff development on workers' job performance and optimal productivity in public secondary schools in Osun State, Nigeria. The study used the ex-post-facto research design. Three research questions and three hypotheses were generated and tested using questionnaire items structured on four points Likert scale. The instrument was administered to a purposely selected population of 152 respondents while 134 questionnaires were returned. Data generated were analyzed using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and Multiple Regression Analysis to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The result of the first analysis revealed that workers' training does not significantly affect workers' performance; the Result also showed that there was no significant relationship between development and workers' optimal job productivity and that in-service training and development had an insignificant combined effect on workers' productivity. The study, therefore, recommended that schools should design proper and functioning in-service training and staff development programmes for their workers to boost their morale, enhance their performance and in addition ensure that workers training are conducted frequently to ensure they cope with changing technological environment and organizational climate in schools.

In Ghana, Hervie and Winful (2018) worked on Enhancing Teachers' Performance through (Training and Development in Ghana Education Service (A Case Study of Ebenezer Senior High School). The study aimed to examine the training and development of teachers and how it enhances their performance in delivery under the Ghana Education Service (GES). The performance of teachers is of primary importance to every country and Ghana is not an exception. Teachers are a source of encouragement to their students because of the developed | relationship and in addition, provide instructions in their respective academic areas. The relatively poor performance of students in recent times has led to this study. The study was based on a case study and quantitative research design. A simple random sampling technique was used to select the [respondents (teachers) of the study. A total of 40 questionnaires were distributed out of which 30 representing 75% were retrieved. The research instrument (teachers' in-service training questionnaire) was designed to have both open and close-ended items. The findings of the study revealed that poor performance of teachers was due to lack of frequent in-service training, lack of teaching and learning materials, lack of incentives and motivation, and improper

supervision.

Teachers Professional Programme and Effectiveness

Yusuf and Fashiku (2016) carried out an empirical study on Professional Development programme: a tool for improving teachers' productivity in junior secondary schools in the North Central Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria. The design of the study was a descriptive survey carried out ex-post facto. The population of the study comprised all the teachers and principals in public junior secondary schools in North Central Geopolitical Zone. The sample of the study was made up of 975 principals and teacher respondents who were randomly selected from 75 schools in the studied area. Two research questions were raised and two hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. A self-designed questionnaire titled "Professional Development Programme and Teachers' Productivity (PDPTP)" as well as an interview schedule titled "Approaches to Professional Development" (APD) were used to elicit information from the respondents. The instruments were validated by six experts from two Departments in the Faculty of Education of Obafemi Awolowo University. The reliability of the questionnaire was ensured through the test-retest method which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.72. The data collected were analyzed using percentage and Pearson's Product Moment Correlation statistical method of data analysis. The study revealed that; cluster type seminars, mentoring, on-the-job training and in-service training approaches among others, were used by the government in teachers' professional training programmes. Also, teachers were found to be selected for professional development programmes based on their; qualifications, years of experience, subjects taught and areas of specialization. A significant relationship existed between professional development programmes and teachers' productivity in junior secondary schools of the North Central geopolitical zone of Nigeria ($r_{tab}=0.785$, $r_{cal}=0.195$) at a 0.05 level of significance. Given the findings of the study, it was concluded that teachers' professional development programmes improved teachers' productivity in junior secondary schools of the North Central geopolitical zone of Nigeria. It was therefore recommended that government should not relent efforts in the Professional Development Programme of every teacher as it is germane to their productivity in the geopolitical Zone.

Inductions/Orientation and Effectiveness

Kio (2019) empirically explored the relationship between training and development on teachers' job effectiveness in secondary schools in Rivers State. The investigation utilized the descriptive survey technique. The sample size comprised of the 523 teachers in 29 schools in Rivers West Senatorial District. A simple mean was used to analyze the research questions while Chi-Square was used to test the null hypothesis at a 0.05% level of significance. Based on the finding after critically analyzing the data, the study unequivocally reveals that there is a significant relationship between mentoring and coaching and teachers

job effectiveness, a strong positive significant relationship between seminar, conference and workshop and teachers job effectiveness; a strong positive significant relationship between induction and orientation and teachers job effectiveness; but a weak significant relationship between a significant relationship between acquisition of higher education qualification and teachers job effectiveness in secondary schools in Rivers State. This implies to all of the variables studies except for acquisition of higher education programme is capable of influencing the job effectiveness of teachers in secondary schools in Rivers State. Based on the major findings and conclusions of the study, the researcher recommended that school proprietors should endeavour to provide more opportunities for teachers to participate in training courses to learn and improve upon their job effectiveness.

Mentoring and Effectiveness

Davies (2015) carried out a study that seeks to investigate the relationship between training and development and effectiveness of academic staff in selected universities in South-South, Nigeria, Using mentioning and coaching; seminar, conference and workshop; induction and orientation; and acquisition of higher qualification as a dimension for training and development and effective teaching, research publication, counseling and research student supervision as measures of effectiveness. The study adopted a correlational design method, while a simple random technique was used to administer the questionnaire which served as the primary source of data collection.

A sample size of 384 was drawn from a population of 9706 academic staff in the universities in South-South, Nigeria which comprises federal, state and private-owned universities using the Taro Yamane's formula. The null hypotheses were tested using the spearman rank-order correlation co-efficient, aided by the statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 21, at a 5% level of significance. The study reveals that there is a positive relationship between mentoring and coaching; seminars, conferences and workshops; induction and orientation; and acquisition of higher qualification and job effectiveness of academic staff in the selected universities in South-South, Nigeria. Based on the finding, the researcher recommended that management of both government and private-owned universities should give more opportunities to academic staff to undergo training and development programmes and those opportunities should be transparently done.

METHODOLOGY

The researcher adopted the correlational research design for the study. A correlational research design is a type of research design where a researcher seeks to understand what kind of relationships two or more variables have with one another. In simple terms, correlational research seeks to find out if two or more variables are related and, if so, in what way. The design was adopted because the study intends to examine the relationship between two variables: teacher capacity development and effectiveness. The population of the study

was 2776 teachers that were drawn from public secondary schools in five (5) Local Government Areas of Bayelsa State. Kolokuma/Opokuma Local Government Area (325 teachers); Ogbia Local Government Area (643 teachers); Ekeremor Local Government Area (264 teachers); Nembe Local Government (163 teachers) and Yenegoa Local Government. Area (1381 teachers). (Source: Bayelsa State Post Primary School Board, 2019). Please find in appendix 5, the table of the population of the study. The Krejcie and Morgan formula for sample determination was used to determine the sample size. The formula gave the sample size to be 335 teachers from a population of 2776 teachers in secondary schools in three local government areas in Bayelsa State. (Please find in appendix 6, the Krejcie and Morgan formula sample determination). The simple random sampling method was used to select 335 teachers from the total population. This means that each of the 335 teachers has an equal chance of participating in this research as a respondent. The instruments used for data collection in this study were two sets of instruments: The teachers Capacity Development Questionnaire (TCDQ) and the Teachers Job Effectiveness Questionnaire (TJEQ). The first instrument is a self-constructed instrument titled "Teacher's Capacity Development Questionnaire (TCDQ)," it was divided into two sections (A and B). Section A consisted of items on personal data such as age, gender, marital status etc., and section B contained statement items that will focus on teacher capacity development. B The second instrument "Teachers Job Effectiveness Questionnaire (TJEQ)," was also self-constructed and that consist of 34 associated items. Both TCDQ and TJEQ were structured on a 4-point Likert scale of strongly Agree (SA)=4, Agree (A)=3, Disagree (D)=2 and Strongly Disagree (SD)=1. Respondents are expected to choose one option for each statement item. To ensure the face and content validity of the instrument, the draft copy was submitted to the supervisor and two other experts in the department of educational management of the university. The internal consistency method using Cronbach Alpha reliability statistic was used to calculate the reliability coefficient. The Cronbach Alpha is suitable because the instrument is sectioned 9 and one time administered. In-Service training subscale was calculated to be 0.77, ICT training land Teacher Development Programme subscales were calculated to be 0.82 and 0.85 respectively, Induction and Orientation subscale was calculated to be 0.71 while mentoring 9subscale was 0.75 and teacher job effectiveness subscale was calculated to be 0.74. The various I reliability coefficients are high enough and guarantee the use of the instrument for the study.

Table 3.1

Cronbach alpha values of the statement items

	Variables	Alpha Value (a)	No. of Items
1	In-Service Training	0.77	6
2	ICT Training	0.82	6
3	Teacher Development	0.85	5

	Programme		
4	Induction and Orientation	0.71	5
5	Mentoring	0.75	5
6	Effectiveness	0.74	11

Source: SPSS Output-Version 21

The research instruments were personally distributed by the researcher with the help of three research assistants. These research assistants were trained by the researcher on how to guide the respondents to fill the research instrument. The distribution of frequencies represented in tables was used to analyze the demographic data of the respondents. The research questions were answered with the use of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) while the hypotheses were tested using simple linear regression with the aid of the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS), computer software (version 21).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

RQ1: What is the relationship between teacher in-service training and teachers' effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State?

Table 4.7

Pearson Correlation Analysis between In-service training and Effectiveness.

		INSERVICE _TRAINING	TEACHERS_ EFFECTIVE NESS
IN_SERVICE_TRAINING	Pearson Correlation	1	.880**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	301	301
	Pearson Correlation	.880**	1
TEACHERS_EFFECTIVENESS		.000	
	Sig. (2-tailed)		
	N	301	301

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Research Data, 2020. SPSS Output.

Table 4.7 above reported a Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient (r-value) of 0.880** probability value of 0.000. This result indicates that there is a strong positive significant relationship between in-service training and teacher's effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State. Therefore, a strong positive relationship exists between training and teachers effectiveness

in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

RQ2: What is the relationship between teacher Information, Communication and Technology (ICT) training and teachers' effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State?

Table 4.7

Pearson Correlation Analysis between In-service training and Effectiveness.
Correlations

	INSERVICE _TRAINING	TEACHERS_ EFFECTIVE NESS
	1	.851**
ICT _TRAINING		
Pearson Correlation		.851**
Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
N	301	301
TEACHERS_EFFECTIVENESS		
Pearson Correlation	.851**	1
Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
N	301	301

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Research Data, 2020. SPSS Output.

Data in table 4.8 above reveals a Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient (r-value) of 0.851** and probability value of 0.000. This result indicates that there is a strong positive significant relationship between teacher Information, Communication and Technology (ICT) training and effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State. Thus, when teacher ICT training increases, teachers' effectiveness increases.

HO₁: There is no significant relationship between teacher in-service training and teacher effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Table 4.12

Simple Linear Regression Analyses between In-service Training and Effectiveness[^]

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	3.222	1.035		3.114	.002
IN-SERVICE CE	1.631	.051	.880	32.019	.000

a. Dependent Variable: TEACHERS_EFFECT

Source: Research Data, 2020. SPSS Output.

Table 4.12 above reveals that at a $p < 0.05$ and a $T = 32.019$ and beta of .880; the direct effect and influence of in-service training on teachers' effectiveness is statically significant and association is high. Thus, satisfying the first model requirement for the assessment of the relationship between in-service training and teachers' effectiveness. Therefore, the hypothesis was rejected because of the PV (0.000) < 0.05 level of significance and the all term I hypothesis was accepted.

HO₂: There is no significant relationship between teacher ICT training and teachers effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.

Table 4.13

Simple Linear Regression Analyses between teacher ICT training and Effectiveness

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	5.607	1.096		5.114	.000
ICT CE	1.830	.065	.851	28.046	.000

a. Dependent Variable: TEACHERS_EFFECT

Source: Research Data, 2020. SPSS Output.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

The following findings emerged from the study based on the research questions and the hypotheses tested.

1. *There is a strong positive relationship between teacher in-service training and teacher effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.*
2. *There is a strong positive significant relationship between teacher Information Communication and Technology (ICT) training and effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.*

3. *There is a strong positive significant relationship between teachers' professional development programmes and teacher effectiveness in secondary schools in Bayelsa State.*
4. *There is a weak positive relationship between teaching induction/orientation and teachers' effectiveness in secondary schools in Bayelsa State.*
5. *There is a strong positive significant relationship between mentorship and teacher: effectiveness in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State.*

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study examined the relationship between teachers' capacity development and teachers' effectiveness in public secondary school in Bayelsa State; five research questions and hypotheses were analyzed and the result as presented below:

Relationship between In-Service Training and Teachers' Effectiveness
 The result of the analysis shows a significant level <0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$), $r = 0.880$. This implies 'there is a strong positive relationship between in-service training and teachers' effectiveness. This implies that an increase in in-service training will lead to an increase in teachers' effectiveness. The result of this study is in concordance with that of Emem (2014) who posit that there is a positive and significant difference between teachers who attended in-service training and those who did not on their teaching effectiveness. In the same vein, the finding of Khan and Abdullah (2019) collaborated with that of this study as they revealed that there exist positive and strong relations between training and development and productivity of the teachers of Kurdistan. The finding of this study is in disagreement with that of Fejoh and Faniran (2016) who established revealed that workers' training does not significantly affect workers' performance, and further stated that there was no significant relationship between development and workers' optimal job productivity and that in-service training and development had an insignificant combined effect on workers' productivity.

Relationship between Teachers ICT Training and Teachers' Effectiveness
 The outcome of this analysis shows a significant level <0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$), $r = 0.851$. This implies there is a strong positive relationship between ICT training and teacher effectiveness. The import of this finding assumes that when teachers embark on ICT training there will be an increase in their job effectiveness. The outcome of this study collaborates with that of Ghavifekr and Rosdy (2015) whose study reveals that ICT integration has great effectiveness for both teachers and the students. Again the finding of this study is in line with Lamidi (2014) who asserts that generally when teachers are trained it enhances their productivity and effectiveness.

Relationship between Teacher Professional Development and Teachers'

Effectiveness The finding showed that there is a strong positive relationship of $p < 0.05$ ($0.00 < 0.05$), $\rho = 0.775$ between teachers professional development programmes and effectiveness. Teacher professional development includes but is not limited to seminars, conferences and workshops. This study implies that when teachers are exposed to teachers' professional development programmes it increases their job effectiveness. The outcome of this study is in line with that of Yusuf and Fashiku (2016) whose study found teachers' professional development programmes such as seminars, mentoring, on the job training etc improved teachers' productivity in junior secondary schools of the North Central geopolitical zone of Nigeria. In the same vein, Woko (2017) and Rahman et al., (2011) concluded that teachers professional development positively relates to effectiveness. The former asserts that there is a positive relationship between seminars, conferences and workshops and acquisition of higher qualification and job performance of academic staff in universities in Rivers State while the latter affirms that teacher training was positively related to effective teaching. The results of the study also indicated that there is a significant correlation between teachers training and student test result. Furthermore, this study agrees with the finding of Ekpoh, et al. (2013), whose finding reveals that teachers who participated in staff development programmes were more effective in their job performance than those who did not, in terms of knowledge of the subject matter, classroom management, teaching methods and evaluation of student's work. However, the outcome of this study disagrees with Yusman (2011) whose study indicated that there is no significant relationship between teacher capacity development and students' academic performance

Relationship between Induction/Orientation and Teachers' Effectiveness

The finding showed that there is a weak positive relationship of $p < 0.05$ ($0.04 < 0.05$), $\rho = 0.167$ between teachers professional development programmes and teachers effectiveness. Upon further research, the implication of this finding is that induction/orientation does not positively impact teachers' effectiveness. This outcome is in divergence with the popular belief that induction/orientation of new staff positively affects their job performance. Kio (2019) found a strong positive significant relationship between induction and orientation and teachers job effectiveness in secondary schools in Rivers State. The study is contradictory to that of Salau. et al. (2014) revealed that induction significantly influences staff attitude and behaviour towards organizational effectiveness. This means that a well-packaged induction programme will positively influence staff attitude.

Relationship between Mentoring and Teachers' Effectiveness

The result of the analysis shows a significant level $p < 0.05$ ($0.000 < 0.05$), $r = 0.844$. This implies there is a strong positive relationship between mentoring and effectiveness. This implies that an increase in mentoring will lead to an increase in teachers' effectiveness. The result of this study is in concordance with that of Davies (2015) whose study revealed that there is a positive

relationship between mentoring and coaching and job effectiveness of academic staff in the selected universities in South-South. Again this finding is in agreement with that of Javed and Iqbal (2015) and Amin, et al. (2018) the former found that mentoring helped teachers to establish goals and fulfil their career-related needs. The effectiveness of teachers and their pedagogical skills could be improved with the mechanism of mentoring, which generated self-confidence, enthusiasm and communication skills. It motivated teachers to accept challenges, find the solution of the problems and learn to manage stress while the latter disclosed that mentoring plays a vital role in shaping working behaviours of teachers, enabling them to perform their duties, using the teaching skills learnt from the mentors during mentoring

CONCLUSION

Based on the finding after critically analyzing the data, the study unambiguously reveals that in-service training, which is relevant courses and activities in which a teacher may participate to upgrade his/her professional knowledge, skills and competence in the teaching profession has a significant positive relationship with teachers effectiveness. The study concludes that in-service training enhances teachers' effectiveness the most. The study further concluded that ICT training of teachers, teachers professional development programme such as seminar, conference, workshop etc and mentoring significantly enhances teachers' effectiveness, thus when this variable increases all things being equal, teachers effectiveness increases proportionally. Lastly, the study concluded that induction and orientation do not significantly enhance teacher effectiveness, which means that when induction and orientation increase teachers' effectiveness; does not increase and vice versa.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

- *Government and school heads should pay more attention to in-service training, as the study reveals that it can enhance teachers' effectiveness the most. Teaching should undergo in-service training at least once a term.*
- *Government should make it mandatory for all teachers in public secondary schools to be ICT compliant. Since most government schools lack ICT gadgets, the government should bear the cost of providing ICT gadgets and also ensure that teachers are regularly trained on the use of ICT gadgets.*
- *The ministry of education through its relevant agencies should at periodic intervals organize general and specialized seminars, workshops, conferences etc for teachers as it is a condition for teachers' effectiveness.*
- *Since the study reveals that induction and orientation do not enhance teachers effectiveness, the scarce resources of the school should be used*

on other aspects of teacher capacity development that enhance teachers' effectiveness.

- *School heads should continue to assign new and young teachers to older and experienced teachers for mentoring since the study reveals that it enhances teachers' effectiveness. Those school heads that are yet to embrace the practice of pairing teachers for mentoring should endeavour to do so.*

Suggestions for Further Studies

Based on the limitation of this study, the following suggestions for further studies were made.

That further research should be carried out on a wider scope. On content scope - other teacher capacity development programmes should be studied in other to ascertain their contribution towards teachers' effectiveness. A moderating variable such as organizational culture should be used to examine the moderating effect between teacher's capacity development and teachers' effectiveness. While for the geographical scope, further research should be carried out with a wider scope to cover other states of the federation to compare the results in Bayelsa state and the new states.

Again, a similar study should be carried out under the same conditions in private secondary schools in Bayelsa State and elsewhere.

Furthermore, a similar study should be carried out in other sectors such as the banking sector, oil and gas sector, manufacturing sector, communication sector etc. to make provision for better comparison of research findings.

The study should be repeated at regular intervals say 3 years from now using different statistical methods to detect possible changes in the findings of this study.

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